

Statistics of Communication Group Activities

Group1 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	4	29	30	178
2020/3/9	4	25	26	153
2020/3/16	4	30	22	167
2020/3/23	4	31	27	129
Total	4	115	105	627

Group2 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	4	26	60	165
2020/3/9	4	28	49	155
2020/3/16	4	26	45	142
2020/3/20	4	31	48	170
2020/3/26	4	27	50	152
Total	4	138	252	784

Group3 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	4	27	160	80
2020/3/11	4	29	141	120
2020/3/17	4	34	135	91
2020/3/24	4	36	131	106
Total	4	126	567	397

Group4 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	4	31	100	78
2020/3/10	4	27	96	75
2020/3/17	4	29	88	85
2020/3/23	4	30	94	75
Total	4	117	378	313

Group5 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/3	4	31	35	111
2020/3/9	4	27	30	103
2020/3/13	4	28	29	97
2020/3/16	4	29	31	112
2020/3/26	4	29	29	102
Total	4	144	154	525

Group6 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/3	4	33	65	190
2020/3/10	4	31	62	181
2020/3/17	4	29	50	169
2020/3/24	4	28	58	146
Total	4	121	235	686

Group7 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	4	30	55	86
2020/3/10	4	28	49	85
2020/3/18	4	27	42	79
2020/3/25	4	33	46	89
Total	4	118	192	339

Group8 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/3	4	35	129	92
2020/3/10	4	29	111	88
2020/3/17	4	33	113	100
2020/3/24	4	29	124	84
Total	4	126	477	364

Group9 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/4	4	31	85	115
2020/3/12	4	29	90	105
2020/3/18	4	33	79	122
2020/3/25	4	36	79	120
Total	4	129	333	462

Group10 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	4	32	80	140
2020/3/11	4	29	73	132
2020/3/17	4	29	75	135
2020/3/26	4	30	74	140
Total	4	120	302	547

Group11 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/4	5	35	94	135
2020/3/13	5	29	88	132
2020/3/19	5	28	85	135
2020/3/26	5	32	89	136
Total	5	124	356	538

Group12 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/4	5	33	100	175
2020/3/13	5	35	105	182
2020/3/19	5	32	100	177
2020/3/26	5	29	96	180
Total	5	129	401	714

Group13 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/3	5	26	108	167
2020/3/10	5	26	95	152
2020/3/17	5	27	101	175
2020/3/23	5	25	99	165
2020/3/27	5	28	109	163
Total	5	132	512	822

Group14 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	5	33	125	201
2020/3/12	5	28	114	199
2020/3/19	5	29	115	191
2020/3/26	5	29	125	196
Total	5	119	479	787

Group15 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/5	5	32	46	65
2020/3/12	5	31	41	60
2020/3/19	5	30	41	69
2020/3/27	5	32	47	63
Total	5	125	175	257

Group16 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/4	5	34	46	130
2020/3/11	5	31	47	109
2020/3/20	5	29	41	99
2020/3/27	5	33	60	120
Total	5	127	194	458

Group17 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	5	29	110	175
2020/3/11	5	37	125	184
2020/3/18	5	29	119	169
2020/3/27	5	36	117	185
Total	5	131	471	713

Group18 Date	students number	workshop speech time (min)	speak times of supervisor	speak times of students
2020/3/2	5	32	86	199
2020/3/11	5	33	84	197
2020/3/18	5	32	87	187
2020/3/27	5	33	84	205
Total	5	130	341	788

Date	Students number	Workshop speech time (min)	Speak times of supervisor	Speak times of students
2020/3/3	5	33	133	195
2020/3/13	5	29	128	175
2020/3/19	5	28	116	187
2020/3/27	5	30	121	185
Total	5	120	498	742

Group20 Date	Students number	Workshop speech time (min)	Speak times of supervisor	Speak times of students
2020/3/2	5	33	90	79
2020/3/10	5	32	72	81
2020/3/16	5	34	81	94
2020/3/24	5	35	68	102
Total	5	134	311	356

